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► **To cite this version:**

L Masci, Laurent Truche, Valérie Magnin, Martine Lanson, A Moya, et al.. Hydrogen adsorption on Ni-functionalized saponites and their precursor gel. *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, 2024, 58, pp.79-92. 10.1016/j.ijhydene.2023.10.314 . hal-04186726

HAL Id: hal-04186726

<https://hal.science/hal-04186726v1>

Submitted on 24 Aug 2023

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Hydrogen adsorption on Ni-functionalized saponites and their precursor gel.

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ABSTRACT

Here we propose to investigate Ni-functionalized saponite (smectite group) as a viable alternative for low cost H₂ storage for land-based applications. The precursor gel used for saponite synthesis is also tested with respect to its H₂ adsorption properties. Adsorption isotherms recorded at 77 K and 1 bar, 298 K and 120 bar indicate that nickel functionalization does not induce a clear structural or chemical control on the adsorption process. However, Ni-pillared saponites outgassed at 70 °C display a four-time enhanced H₂ uptake (up to 0.12 wt% at 77 K and 1 bar) compared to its counterpart outgassed at 150 °C. Another important finding of this study is the surprisingly high H₂ uptakes of the gel (nano-crystallized) precursor, used for the synthesis of saponite samples (up to 0.19 wt% at 77 K and 1 bar, and up to 0.12 wt% at 298 K and 120 bar).

23 KEY-WORDS

24 Clay materials, saponite, H₂ adsorption, isotherms, specific surface area, Ni functionalization,
25 hydrogen storage

26 1. Introduction

27 This last decade has seen an increase of interest for hydrogen (H₂) as a carbon free energy
28 vector that can be stored. If produced by water electrolysis from renewable energy, or from
29 fossil fuels with carbon capture and sequestration, this molecule is a good candidate to replace
30 fossil fuels, for both mobile and stationary applications, because of its high energy density per
31 mass unit (142 MJ/kg) [1–3]. However, one of hydrogen main drawbacks lies in its low
32 volumetric density at ambient temperature and pressure, which requires specific storage
33 technologies. Besides conventional storage methods such as high-pressure gas reservoirs (up
34 to 700 bar at ambient temperature), cryo-compression (supercritical H₂ at 23 K and ~ 300 bar),
35 or metal hydrides (H₂ chemisorption, where the T - P range depends on the chosen metal
36 hydride: typically 25 < T < 300 °C and 1 < P < 10 bar), many solid porous media have been
37 developed to store H₂ through physisorption interactions.

38 Among these materials, Metal Organic Frameworks (MOFs), zeolites, carbon-based nano
39 materials have been thoroughly investigated for their hydrogen gravimetric density (i.e.
40 kg_{H₂}/kg_{material}) reaching up to ~ 9 wt% H₂ at 77 K and 50 bar for these compounds [4–11].
41 Nevertheless, these materials have several disadvantages such as high production costs [12],
42 complex manufacturing processes [13], low stabilities [14], and high toxicities inherent to their
43 chemical composition and nanostructure [15]. Even more important, hydrogen storage
44 materials based on physisorption process suffer from a dramatic loss of storage capacity as

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45 temperature increases above 77 K due to the low enthalpy of H₂ adsorption on these
46 materials, i.e. 5 - 8 kJ/mol [16]. The adsorption capacity of carbon-based nanomaterials
47 typically decreases by one order of magnitude from 77 K to 298 K. For example, H₂ uptake of
48 single-wall carbon nanotubes is ~ 2 wt% H₂ at 77 K and 40 bar, but decreases down to ~ 0.2
49 wt% H₂ at 298 K and 200 bar [11].

50 Clay minerals, like smectites, illites or kaolinites, display interesting H₂ adsorption properties
51 and help to overcome some of the above-mentioned limitations. Smectites in particular are
52 promising materials thanks to their abundance in natural environments, their ease of mass
53 production, their large surface area and their high sorption capacities with respect to a
54 plethora of gases, molecules and dissolved ions. Smectites are formed by a 2:1 layer made of
55 an octahedral sheet filled by Mg²⁺ cations, in between two tetrahedral sheets (also called TOT
56 layers) filled with Si⁴⁺ and Al³⁺ cations in the case of saponite (see Fig. 1a). The charge deficit
57 induced by the replacement of Si⁴⁺ by Al³⁺, is compensated by interlayer cations, here, Na⁺ or
58 Ca⁺. The intercalation of H₂ in the interlayer space, may be favored by: i) strong electrostatic
59 interactions inside the interlayer cavities due to the presence of exchangeable cations (this
60 electrostatic field induces a dipolar moment to H₂ - nominally apolar - and thus promotes its
61 physisorption), ii) the geometry of the interlayer space which is homogeneous and does not
62 present bottleneck likely to prevent H₂ diffusion, and iii) the size of the interlayer micropore
63 network that can match a few H₂ diameter (2.89 Å) [17]. Hydrogen may also be adsorbed on
64 the basal and edge sites, and in the porosity in between clay particles. The high specific surface
65 area (SSA) of clay minerals, that can reach ~ 400 m²/g for some particular clays such as
66 laponite® [17–19], also make them good sorbents for gases like CO₂ and CH₄ [20–24].

67 Yet, H₂ adsorption capacity of smectites and other clay minerals remains poorly investigated.

68 A maximum gravimetric sorption capacity of ~ 0.2 wt% H₂ was recorded at 77 K and ~ 1 bar H₂

69 pressure for Al-pillared montmorillonite [25], K-bentonite [26] and sepiolite [27]. Edge and

70 Edge et al. [17,28] studied several varieties of laponite[®], which is a registered trademark for a

71 type of smectite, and measured H₂ uptake as a function of temperature and pressure. They

72 reported maximum sorption capacity of ~ 0.1 wt% H₂ at ambient temperature and 140 bar,

73 and up to 0.63 wt% H₂ at 1 bar and 77 K. Recently, Ziemiański & Derkowski [29] investigated

74 H₂ adsorption on montmorillonite and illite at temperatures ranging from 25 °C to 70 °C and

75 pressure up to 145 bar. They concluded that H₂ intercalation within smectite interlayers is

76 strongly dependent on hydration state of the interlayer space, itself controlled by the nature

77 of the exchangeable cation. Under the tested conditions the maximum H₂ uptake never

78 exceeded 0.04 wt%, even if montmorillonite exchanged with tetramethylammonium cation

79 was a noticeable exception displaying an H₂ uptake of 0.1 wt% at 25 °C and 145 bar.

80 At 77 K, high H₂ sorption values on clays and other porous media are well correlated to the

81 specific surface areas and the micropore volume [27,30,31]. However, it remains unclear

82 whether clay minerals micropores suitable for H₂ adsorption are localized inside the interlayer

83 space, on the edges of the 2:1 layer, on the basal surfaces, or in-between the particles. In

84 addition, the ability of the interlayer space to incorporate gases such as CO₂ strongly depends

85 on both the hydration state, and the nature of the charge-balancing cations [23]. The effect

86 of water content is significant as it might control the space available for gas species adsorption

87 and compete with the sorbent gas. Many studies on clays managed to optimize the interlayer

88 space, by addition of molecular species such as transition metal cations or organic molecules

89 [32–34]. To that extent, pillared clays are the most common type of functionalized clay-based

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90 materials as their interlayer space is modified on purpose to create a porous network suitable
91 to enhance the adsorption of a given molecule [25,35–38].
92 In addition to the effect of porosity, several studies on porous materials highlighted the
93 effectiveness of transition metals such as nickel, in increasing the electrostatic field able to
94 attract and polarize hydrogen atoms on diverse material surfaces [39–41]. Beyond its low cost,
95 compared to classically used H₂-catalysts, like platinum or palladium metals, nickel is a natural
96 component of various types of clays [42,43], and may occupy different crystallographic sites
97 in the clay structure.
98 As questions remain open on the links between clays porosity and their H₂ adsorption
99 capacity, we focused on the structural properties of a synthetic saponite in order to decipher
100 the crystal-chemical influence on H₂ physisorption. Several saponite were thus synthesized
101 with a carefully controlled addition of Ni²⁺ cations or Ni⁰ nano-particles to the structure at
102 different potential H₂ adsorption sites (i.e. interlayer space, edges, basal surface, and
103 octahedral sites) in order to probe the adsorption properties of these sites. In addition, the
104 precursor gel used for saponite synthesis was also tested with respect to its H₂ adsorption
105 properties.

2. Materials and methods

2.1 Sample description

2.1.1 Ni-functionalized saponites

with a layer charge of 1.2 e⁻ per O₂₀(OH)₄

Name	S _{BET} m ² /g	S _{μporous} m ² /g	V _{μporous} cm ³ /g	H ₂ uptake		Description
				77 K-1 bar	298 K-120 bar	
				wt% H ₂		
CLAYS						
Sap1.2	31	0	0	0.02	0	Ni-free saponite with a charge layer of 1.2
Sap1.2_Ni-interl.	35	0	0	0.02	-	Na ⁺ exchanged with Ni ²⁺ inside the interlayer space
Sap1.2_Ni-pillars	37	2	0.001	0.01	0	Ni(OH) ₂ pillars inside the interlayer space
Sap1.2_Ni-edges1	37	3	0.001	0.03	0	Ni ²⁺ sorbed on the edges for 2 h
Sap1.2_Ni-edges2	40	6	0.003	0.01	-	Ni ²⁺ sorbed on the edges for 12 h
Sap1.2_Ni-edges3	37	2	0.001	0.03	0	Ni ²⁺ sorbed on the edges for 22 days
Sap1.2_Ni-surface	9	0	0	0.01	-	Ni ⁰ nanoparticles on surface
Gel_Sap1.2	145	77	0.029	0.19	0.12	Precursor gel
STANDARDS						
MOF-177	3856	3835	1.547	1.22	0.51	
<i>Furukawa et al., 2007</i>	4630	n.a.	n.a.	1.25*	n.a.	
<i>Li and Yang, 2007</i>	3100	n.a.	n.a.	1.50	n.a.	
<i>Voskuilen et al., 2012</i>	4126	n.a.	1.67	n.a.	0.55	
<i>Zacharia et al., 2010</i>	3400 - 4100**	n.a.	1.3 - 1.6	n.a.	0.59	
Activated Carbon	872	523	0.213	1.38	-	
Y-Zeolite	677	630	0.242	0.03	-	
LapRD	347	340	0.239	0.26	0.12	
<i>Edge, 2014</i>	399***			0.24	~ 0.11	
- not measured						
n.a. not available						
* measured at 0.8 bar						
** for densities d = 0.39 - 0.51						
*** calculated from DFT calculations						

Caption: H₂ modeling applied to H₂ isotherms realized at 77 K

Table 1. Description and summary of textural parameters (S_{BET}, S_{μporous}, V_{μporous}) and H₂ uptake for all clay materials from this study (*Sap1.2*, Ni-saponites, and *Gel_Sap1.2*), and for standards used in this study and from the literature [17,31,44–46].

Saponite with the structural composition Si_{8-X}Al_XMg₆O₂₀(OH)₄Na_X, a layer charge deficit X = 1.2 (sample named as *Sap1.2*) and a density of d ~ 2.3 g/cm³ [47] was initially synthesized as a template for Ni functionalization (see protocol at the next section). Two Ni-saponite samples were synthesized by addition of Ni²⁺ into the interlayer space. The first sample, named *Sap1.2_Ni-interl.*, has the structural composition Si_{6.8}Al_{1.2}Mg₆O₂₀(OH)₄Ni_{0.6} with hydrated Ni²⁺ replacing interlayer Na⁺ cations. The second configuration, named *Sap1.2_Ni-pillars*, corresponds to the formation of Ni(OH)₂ pillars, creating a porous network inside the interlayer space that is supposed to prevent its complete collapse during thermal treatments prior to volumetric analysis [37]. In addition, three different Ni-saponite samples with Ni²⁺ located on the edges were also prepared. According to available protocols [48,49], various

124 duration of sorption experiments led to three samples with different extent of Ni octahedral
125 sheet on particle outer edges : i) with Ni²⁺ cations only adsorbed on the edges of the TOT layer,
126 named *Sap1.2_Ni-edges1*, ii) with partial recrystallization of octahedral and tetrahedral sites
127 from the edges, and Ni²⁺ incorporation into the new octahedral sites, named *Sap_Ni-edges2*,
128 and iii) with complete structural Ni²⁺ recrystallization, named *Sap1.2_Ni-edges3*. An additional
129 configuration was tested by addition of Ni⁰ nanoparticles deposited on the surface of *Sap1.2*
130 sheets, and is called *Sap1.2_Ni-surface*. All atomic structures of saponites are shown in Fig. 1,
131 and listed in Table 1. The gel precursor used for the hydrothermal synthesis of Na-saturated
132 saponite, named *Gel_Sap1.2*, was also analysed for its H₂ adsorption properties. The apparent
133 density of the gel was measured volumetrically and was found to be around 1.0 g/cm³.
134 All syntheses and analytical measurements were carried out at ISTerre laboratory (Grenoble,
135 France), excepted if clearly mentioned.

136

137

Figure 1

Fig. 1. Crystal-chemical configurations of saponites with Ni addition to the structure (basic structure modified with permission from Paineau et al. [50], after Grim et al. [51]). They are described as followed: a) saponite Na-saturated sample (*Sap1.2*); b) and c) saponites whose interlayer space was modified with Ni²⁺ cations sorption (*Sap1.2_Ni-interl.*), or Ni(OH)₂ pillaring (*Sap1.2_Ni-pillars*); d) to f) saponites whose edges were modified with Ni²⁺ sorption (*Sap1.2_Ni-edge1*), partial crystallization (*Sap1.2_Ni-edge2*), or complete crystallization of Ni²⁺ into new octahedral sites (*Sap1.2_Ni-edge3*); g) saponite whose surface was modified by sorption of Ni⁰ nanoparticles (*Sap1.2_Ni-surface*).

2.1.2 Standards

In addition to saponites, several porous materials previously described in the literature have been characterized as N₂ and H₂ adsorption standards to validate our volumetric measurements protocol. A Metal-Organic Framework (*MOF-177*, CAS number 676593-65-0, density $d = 0.35 \text{ g/cm}^3$) and an activated carbon (*Activated carbon*, CAS number: 7440-44-0) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich®. Finally, a zeolite (*Y-zeolite*) was provided by Micromeritics® as an internal standard for N₂ volumetric measurements, and a commercial laponite® (*LapRD*) obtained from Laporte PLC® (ref: 5765) was also used.

2.2 Experimental protocol

Synthesis of saponite (*Sap1.2*) was carried out using hydrothermal method from a sol gel solution according to a well-established protocol [35,52,53]. The precursor gel (*Gel_Sap1.2*) was prepared from saturated Mg(NO₃)₂ and Al(NO₃)₃ solutions, Na₂CO₃, and Tetra Ethyl Ortho Silicate (TEOS) solutions as Mg, Al, Na and Si sources, respectively, in proportions corresponding to the stoichiometric formula. The saponite synthesis was achieved at 400 °C and 400 bar of water confining pressure during 4 weeks using an externally heated Morey-type pressure vessel fitted with an internal silver tubing containing 8 g of *Gel_Sap1.2*. After the hydrothermal synthesis, saponite sample was Na-saturated by mixing 1 mol/L aqueous solution of NaCl with saponite for 24 h before separation of the solid fraction by centrifugation (1 cycle of 10 min at 9000 rpm). Excess NaCl was removed by rinsing the solid 4 times with deionized water followed by steps of centrifugation to isolate the solid fraction (4 cycles of 10 min at 12000 rpm).

Part of the resulting crystallized *Sap1.2* was afterwards mixed with a solution of NiCl₂ at 0.2 mol/L and matured during 2 x 45 min at ambient temperature, leading to the *Sap1.2_Ni-interl.*

169 The *Sap1.2_Ni-pillars* was obtained using an annealing route: an aliquot of *Sap1.2_Ni-interl.*
170 suspension was placed into a 23 mL Parr vessel with NaOH solution at 10^{-5} mol/L at 80 °C for
171 12 days. As a result, Ni(OH)₂ pillars, i.e. isolated “island-like” fragments of a Ni(OH)₂ octahedral
172 sheet, were crystallized inside the interlayer space.

173 *Sap1.2_Ni-edges1,2,3* samples were prepared from solutions mixed with milli-Q® water
174 (conductivity of 18.2 MOhm.cm) and chemicals of ACS reagent grade. The synthesis was
175 conducted in a thermostated glass vessel at 25 °C with constant stirring of the suspension at
176 250 rpm. An inert atmosphere was maintained by bubbling Ar purified by a solutions setup
177 (H₂SO₄ 0.1 M, NaOH 0.1 M and NaCl 0.25 M). 100 mL of *Sap1.2* suspension at 9.1 g/L was
178 added to 39 mL milli-Q water in which 2.118 g of NaCl salt has been previously dissolved in
179 order to obtain a high ionic strength and to saturate the interlayer space with Na⁺. Finally, 1
180 mL of SiO₂ solution at 0.0725 M was added to compensate the *Sap1.2* dissolution and to allow
181 the epitaxial growth on the edges of the saponite layers [48]. The pH was adjusted and
182 maintained at 7.3 by automated NaOH (0.02 M) addition using a Metrohm® 716 DMS device
183 running with Tiamo™ software. After pH equilibration for 5 hours, 5 mL of a solution containing
184 NiCl₂ at 23.8 mM and NaCl at 0.25 M was added. The final suspension has a solid-to-liquid
185 ratio of 6.3 g/L, a Ni aqueous concentration of 820 μM, a Si_{aq} concentration of 500 μM and a
186 high ionic strength (NaCl) 0.25 M. Afterwards, three samples of 50 mL of this suspension were
187 collected at 2h, 22h and 22 days. Each sample was filtered through a 0.1 μm nitrocellulose
188 filter, washed twice with milli-Q® water and then freeze-dried.

189 Saponite decoration with Ni⁰ nanoparticles (*Sap1.2_Ni-surface*) was carried out *via* polyol
190 method at LEPMI laboratory (Grenoble, France). Ni⁰ nanoparticles were generated from the
191 reduction of dissolved Ni salt in the presence of the *Sap1.2* dispersed in ethylene glycol (EG)
192 that acts as solvent, reducing agent and stabilizer. Addition of monosodium citrate as

193 surfactant allows to better control the size of the particles. In details, 890 mg of NiCl₂.6H₂O
194 and 1.180 g of monosodium citrate were mixed in 100 mL EG in a 250 mL flask. After complete
195 dissolution of the salts, pH was adjusted to 10 by dropwise addition of a 5 wt% solution of
196 KOH in EG. After addition of 175 mg of previously synthesized *Sap1.2*, the mixture was heated
197 under gentle stirring to 160 °C for 20 hours. After cooling down to room temperature, the final
198 product was collected by centrifugation (9000 rpm – 20 min), rinsed several times with
199 deionized water, and dried at 60 °C for 1 hour.

2.3 X-ray diffraction

201 XRD patterns were recorded on powders using a Bruker D8 diffractometer operated in the
202 Bragg-Brentano geometry at 40 kV and 40 mA, and equipped with a SolX Si(Li) solid state
203 detector from Baltic Scientific Instruments®. Intensities were recorded at 0.04° 2θ step
204 intervals from 2 to 20° 2θ range (6 s counting time per step – CuKα₁₊₂ radiation). The
205 diffractometer was also equipped with a MHG Messtechnik® humidity controller coupled to
206 an Anton Paar® CHC+ chamber, to perform analyses at various relative humidities (RH = 3%,
207 10% and 80%).

208 Powder X-ray diffraction for *Sap1.2* and *Gel_Sap1.2* was also carried out on the MORPHEUS
209 platform of Laboratoire de Physique des Solides (Orsay, France) using a copper rotating anode
210 (RU H3R, Rigaku Corp., Japan) operating at a wavelength $\lambda = 0.1542$ nm delivered by Osmic
211 optics. The diffractometer is equipped with a two-dimensional mar345 detector (marXperts
212 GmbH, Germany) with 150 μm pixel size, placed at 150 mm from the sample: glass capillary (1
213 mm diameter) filled with powder material (saponite or gel). It has been heated inside a
214 furnace at 150 °C for 6 hours under primary vacuum conditions and then sealed. The two-
215 dimensional diffraction patterns consist in concentric rings with constant angular intensity.

216 Background signals from air and from the capillary are subtracted based on the measurement
217 of the absorption of the direct beam by the sample. The measured intensity is also corrected
218 from the geometrical factor to be used for a planar detector, the polarisation factor and the
219 X-ray absorption between the sample and a given pixel on the detector.

220 **2.4 N₂ and H₂ adsorption experiments**

221 Unless specifically mentioned, all materials were initially degassed at 150 °C for 6 h under real
222 secondary vacuum at 4×10^{-3} mbar. Nitrogen and hydrogen physisorption experiments were
223 carried out at 1 bar and 77 K, using a volumetric gas sorption instrument ASAP 2020 PLUS from
224 Micromeritics Instruments®. From N₂ isotherms, the specific surface area of powdered
225 samples (150 - 500 mg) was estimated using the Brunauer–Emmet–Teller (S_{BET}) equation in
226 the $0.05 \leq P/P_0 \leq 0.3$ interval of relative pressure and using a cross-sectional area of 16.2 \AA^2
227 for molecular N₂. For microporous samples, the free space measurements were performed by
228 a BET analysis until $P/P_0 = 0.4$, before outgassing again the samples to prevent He retention
229 previously used for dead volume measurement. Data analyses were performed using ASAP
230 2020 Plus software from Micromeritics®. The presence of micropores in the sample ($\phi_{\text{pore}} < 2$
231 nm) was assessed using the t-plot method [54].

232 Hydrogen isotherms were acquired with an equilibration interval of 60 seconds for routine
233 analysis (~ 5 to 8 hours for a complete isotherm acquisition). An ultra-high purity grade of H₂
234 (99.999% purity) was used for the adsorption experiments.

235 High pressure hydrogen experiments were performed at 298 K and 120 bar at the Neel
236 Institute using a PCT Hiden® IMI system apparatus and data analyses were performed using
237 Isochema® software. Around 200 to 600 mg of powdered samples were inserted inside a steel
238 sample holder (internal volume ~ 200 mm³), with a small amount of glass wool to prevent

239 powder removal during vacuuming steps. Adsorption and desorption isotherms were
240 performed with an equilibration time of 15 - 30 minutes for routine analysis. As for low
241 pressure analysis, each sample was heated and outgassed at 150 °C for at least 6 hours prior
242 to each measurement.

243 **2.5 Thermogravimetric analyses (DSC-TGA)**

244 TG/DSC curves were recorded on a TGA/DSC3+ Mettler Toledo® instrument. Approximately
245 50 mg of sample (+/- 30 mg) were placed in a 150 µL alumina crucible. The experiments were
246 carried out under N₂ atmosphere with a flow rate of 20 mL/min. Sample mass loss and
247 associated thermal effects were recorded from 25 to 900 °C using a constant heating ramp of
248 5 °C/min. In order to identify the different mass loss steps, the TGA first derivative (rate of
249 mass loss) was used.

250 **2.6 Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM)**

251 Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM) measurements were conducted to measure *Sap1.2* particles
252 topography and particles size. The device used was a MFP-3D microscope with contact mode
253 from Asylum Research® (Santa Barbara, USA). The maximum range of the piezo scanner is 120
254 µm in the planar direction (x,y) and 15 µm in the vertical direction (z). The microscope is
255 isolated inside a chamber and mounted on top of a vibration isolation control unit from
256 Herzan®. Topography images were acquired in contact mode using triangular silicon nitride
257 (PNP-TR from NanoWorld®) cantilevers with a nominal length of 200 µm, width of 28 µm and
258 a thickness of 500 nm. Before each experiment, the deflection sensitivity was determined and
259 the spring constants were routinely calibrated using the thermal method, resulting in 100-200
260 pN/nm. The obtained data were processed using the AR and WSxM softwares [55].

261 Prior to AFM measurement, sample of *Sap1.2* was deposited on mica substrate. First, the
262 powder was dispersed in Milli-Q® water (1 mg/mL) and 100 µL of the solution was deposited
263 on the mica plate, dried at room temperature for 1 hour and blown with N₂.

264 **2.7 Transmission Electron Microscopy imaging (TEM)**

265 Transmission Electron Microscopy images were acquired using a Jeol® 2010 microscope
266 (CMTC-INPG) with a LaB₆ filament and operating at 200 kV. The images were collected with a
267 2048 × 2048 pixels CCD camera (Gatan® Ultrascan 1000 XP).

269 **3. Results**

270 **3.1 XRD results**

271 XRD measurements on Ni-saponites whose interlayer space was modified with Ni²⁺ exchange
272 (*Sap1.2_Ni-interl.*) or pillaring (*Sap1.2_Ni-pillars*) are displayed in Fig. 2a. At RH = 80%, Ni
273 intercalation in the structure implies a slight shift of the apparent d_{001} -spacing from 15.12 Å
274 to 14.62 Å and 14.24 Å for cations exchange or pillaring in the interlayer respectively,
275 compared to the initial Na-saturated *Sap1.2*. Without pillaring, decreasing RH from 80 to 10%,
276 induces noticeable difference between Na-saturated (*Sap1.2*) and Ni²⁺ exchanged saponite
277 (*Sap1.2_Ni-interl.*). One can observe that Ni²⁺ has a higher water affinity than Na⁺, as
278 *Sap1.2_Ni-interl.* apparent d_{001} -spacing is still at 14.15 Å at RH = 10%, while the apparent d_{001} -
279 spacing of *Sap1.2* has already decreased to 12.13 Å, consistently with previous results [56].
280 Further drying of *Sap1.2_Ni-interl.* down to RH = 3% leads to a marked decrease of the
281 apparent d_{001} -spacing from 14.15 Å to 12.20 Å. This phenomenon is due to partial interlayer
282 cation dehydration. Slight differences do exist when Na⁺ is exchanged by Ni²⁺ in the interlayer.

283 This is shown by apparent d_{001} -spacing at RH = 3% of 11.94 Å and 12.20 Å for *Sap1.2* and
284 *Sap1.2_Ni-interl.*, respectively (Fig. 2a). Dehydration phenomenon has only a minor effect on
285 *Sap1.2_Ni-pillars*, whose apparent d_{001} -spacing is 14.24 Å at RH = 80% and 13.71 Å at RH = 3%,
286 confirming the presence of Ni(OH)₂ pillars in the interlayer space. Indeed the presence of these
287 pillars prevents the collapse of the interlayer as previously reported [57].

288 Saponites whose edges were modified by nickel addition (i.e. *Sap1.2_Ni-edges1,2,3*) evidence
289 almost no apparent d_{001} -spacing shift compared to *Sap1.2* at RH = 80%, with $d = 15.02$ Å for
290 the three samples and $d = 15.12$ Å for *Sap1.2* (Fig. 2b). This observation confirms incorporation
291 (adsorbed or incorporated) of Ni²⁺ cations on the edges and not inside the interlayer space. In
292 Fig. 2a and 2b, only the 00 l reflections are observed due to the geometry of the experiment
293 and the use of oriented preparations.

294 The powder X-ray diffractogram of *Sap1.2* is shown in Fig. 2c. One observes the 00 l reflections
295 characteristic of the coherent stacking of the TOT sheets. In addition, hk bands with typical
296 sawtooth profiles are observed rather than hkl reflections owing to turbostratism (systemic
297 occurrence of stacking disorder in between successive layers). The in-plane coherence lengths
298 are given by the slope of the rising edge of the bands [58]. It is resolution limited here, which
299 only allows us to conclude that they are larger than a few tens of nanometer. The 02,11 and
300 20,13 bands are still visible for *Gel_Sap1.2*, with a much smoother rising edge however,
301 indicative of very small fragments of octahedral/tetrahedral sheets constitutive of TOT layers,
302 and representative of a nano-crystallized component. An additional broad and symmetric
303 hump centered at $2\theta \approx 25^\circ$ is also observed, which may correspond to an amorphous gel
304 component. No 001 peak is observed, due to the intense signal at small angles reflecting the
305 porosity of the assembly of these small solid particles (Fig. 2c).

306
307 **Fig. 2.** XRD patterns of Ni-saponites and *Gel_Sap1.2* in comparison with *Sap1.2* (* for capillary
308 measurement): **(a)** Ni-saponites with modified interlayer space (*Sap1.2_Ni-interl.* and *Sap1.2_Ni-*
309 *pillars*) at different relative humidities RH = 3, 10 and 80%; **(b)** Ni-saponites whose edges were modified
310 (*Sap1.2_Ni-edges1,2,3*) at RH = 80%; **(c)** the precursor gel (*Gel_Sap1.2*).

311 3.2 AFM and TEM imaging

312 Figs. 3a-d show AFM images of a continuous film of *Sap1.2* deposited on a mica plate. Images
313 acquired at a spatial scale from 3 to 0.6 μm and resolution around from 10 to 2.5 nm/px
314 revealed the stacking of *Sap1.2* layers forming irregular shapes (Figs. 3c and 3d). The
315 corresponding height histogram (Fig. 3e) shows the stacking of the saponite layers with an
316 average height of 21.5 nm, in good agreement with the stacking length deduced from powder
317 XRD measurements. Furthermore, the variations of about 1.35 nm observed at lower heights
318 (see inset of Fig. 3e) are compatible with the d values deduced from XRD for smectite
319 monolayers. This result agrees well with the height profile of Fig. 3f that corresponds to the

320 green line on Fig. 3c where height variations across a single TOT sheet can be observed. Such
321 height variation reaches 1.1 - 1.2 nm as shown in Fig. 3c.
322 The comparison of AFM and TEM images shows an almost hexagonal grain shape of the clay
323 sheets for *Sap1.2* (Fig. 3g). Grain sizes are also consistent in between both techniques with an
324 average grain size of 100 to 400 nm in diameter.

Figure 3

325

326 **Fig. 3.** Topographical AFM images of *Sap1.2*: (a,c) height images and (b,d) deflection images of the
327 saponite layers deposited on mica substrate. (e) Height histogram of Fig. 3c showing the size of the
328 agglomerations and the inset showing the distribution for the smallest height. (f) Height profile

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329 corresponding to the horizontal lines in the Fig. 3c which corresponds to the topography of a single
330 (mainly rounded) saponite layer. (g) TEM images of *Sap1.2*.

331 **3.3 TGA results**

332 All samples (*LapRD*, *Sap1.2*, *Sap1.2_Ni-interl.*, *Sap1.2_Ni-pillars*, and *Sap1.2_Ni-edges1,2,3*)
333 show a major weight loss of 6 to 14% from ~ 100 °C up to ~ 250 °C (Fig. 4) corresponding to
334 the removal of interlayer water. The overall amount of water release depends on the initial
335 hydration state, which is imposed by the RH of the room atmosphere prior to the
336 measurement. The *Sap1.2* on the one hand, and both the *Sap1.2_Ni-interl.* and *Sap1.2_Ni-*
337 *pillars* on the other hand display different water loss at 150 °C: ~ 9 and 14 wt%, respectively.
338 More water is attracted and retained by Ni²⁺ and Ni(OH)₂ pillars than by Na⁺ whose hydration
339 energy is lower. However, as RH was not controlled, the overall amount of water release
340 mainly depends on the initially lower hydration state of *Sap1.2* compared to the Ni-saponites.
341 In addition, *Sap1.2_Ni-interl.* and *Sap1.2_Ni-pillars* display a second small weight loss of ~ 2%
342 around 200 °C, and a third loss < 1% around ~ 400 °C. Such a phenomenon is only observed
343 for samples with interlayer Ni. The small weight loss at 200 °C may correspond to the
344 dehydration of remaining water linked to Ni²⁺ or Ni(OH)₂ pillars. Indeed in the case of
345 *Sap1.2_Ni-interl.*, Ni²⁺ cations have the ability to partly retain H₂O molecules from its hydration
346 sphere along dehydration [59,60]. The weight loss observed at 400 °C is well explained by the
347 thermal decomposition of the Ni(OH)₂ pillars [61]. However, in the case of *Sap1.2_Ni-interl.*,
348 it is possible that water produced during the two firsts dehydration steps at 150 °C and 200
349 °C, further reacts with Ni²⁺ in the interlayers to form Ni(OH)₂ pillars during the TGA
350 measurement. The dehydration of these latter pillars explaining the small weight loss
351 observed at 400 °C for *Sap1.2_Ni-interl.*. Finally, another major weight loss is also recorded

352 for all samples at temperature above 700 °C corresponding to the dehydroxylation process,
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3 353 i.e. the loss of OH groups from the structure, which is well-described for trioctahedral
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5 354 smectites at these temperatures [62–64]. It can also be reported that *LapRD*, shows a slightly
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8 355 lower dehydroxylation temperature starting at ~ 700 °C. This shift likely results from the
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10 356 smaller particle size of *LapRD* compared to saponite, thus improving the diffusion of water
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12
13 357 molecules [65].

Figure 4

358 **Fig. 4.** TGA and DTG profiles of Ni-saponites, *Sap1.2* and *LapRD*. Analysis were carried out from 25 °C
359 to 900 °C at a ramp heating of 5 °C/min.

360 3.4 N₂ isotherms and textural characterization

361 Calculations of specific surface area give i) a $S_{\text{BET}} = 31 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$ for *Sap1.2*, ii) a range of S_{BET} from
362 35 to $40 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$ for most of Ni-saponites, and iii) a S_{BET} of $9 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$ for *Sap1.2_Ni-surface* (Table 1).
363 The N_2 isotherms of well-crystallized Ni-saponites are difficult to classify according to the
364 IUPAC (International Union of Pure and Applied Chemistry) terminology (Fig. 5). On the one
365 hand, their global shape present isotherms of type II, characteristic of non-porous materials
366 [66]. The t-plot calculations also indicate the absence of microporosity (e.g. surface and
367 volume of micropores close to zero). On the other hand, the presence of hysteresis loops
368 typical for isotherms of type IV indicate capillary condensation effects occurring inside the
369 pore space of the samples (Figs. 5a-d). Here, all saponites show hysteresis loops of H3/H4
370 types from the IUPAC classification, typical of platy-shaped particles (H3) such as clay minerals
371 [67]. The BJH, HK and DFT calculations were not applied on saponite, as the lack of
372 conventional porosity from N_2 isotherms, i.e. micro- or mesoporosity from the IUPAC
373 classification, could lead to erroneous pore size distributions.

374 N_2 isotherm of *Gel_Sap1.2* differs significantly from other well-crystallized saponite samples
375 as it displays a clear shape of type I at low relative pressures, which indicates the presence of
376 microporosity (i.e. pore size $< 2 \text{ nm}$). It can be related to the intensity increase at small angle
377 in XRD experiments. This is supported by t-plot calculations that give the following surface and
378 a volume of microporosity: $S_{\mu\text{pores}} = 77 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$ and $V_{\mu\text{pores}} = 0.029 \text{ cm}^3/\text{g}$. The specific surface area
379 calculation gives a S_{BET} of $145 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$, which is up to 4 times higher than for its crystallized
380 counterpart *Sap1.2*. Hysteresis loops also reveal capillary condensation in *Gel_Sap1.2* porous
381 structure.

Fig 5. N₂ isotherms carried out at 1 bar and 77 K of *Sap1.2* compared to : (a) *Sap1.2_Ni-interl.* and *Sap1.2_Ni-pillars* ; (b) *Sap1.2_Ni-edges1,2,3* ; (c) *Sap1.2_Ni_surface* ; and (d) *Gel_Sap1.2*. All samples were outgassed at 150 °C prior to analysis.

3.5 H₂ adsorption isotherms

3.5.1 Assessment of H₂ adsorption procedures

Both low and high H₂ pressure isotherms were carried out on *MOF-177*, *Activated carbon*, *Y-zeolite* and *LapRD*, to compare H₂ uptakes with data from literature (Fig. 6; Table 1). At 77 K – 1 bar, the *Activated carbon* and *MOF-177* display the highest H₂ uptakes with 1.38 and 1.22 wt% H₂, respectively (Fig. 6a). For *MOF-177*, our H₂ isotherm indicates a slightly lower uptake than that reported previously [44,45] at 77 K and around 0.8 bar (1.50 wt%). At high pressure (> 100 bar) and 298 K, the comparison of H₂ isotherms from this study and from the literature [17,31,46] for both *MOF-177* and *LapRD*, show a very good agreement with H₂ uptake of 0.12 and 0.50 wt% H₂ at 120 bar and 298 K for *LapRD* and *MOF-177*, respectively (Fig. 6b).

396 Specific surface areas were derived from N₂ isotherms and BET calculations. Our
 397 measurements give a S_{BET} of 3856 m²/g for *MOF-177*, consistent with values from literature
 398 that range from 3100 to 4630 m²/g (see Table 1 and references therein). *Activated carbon* and
 399 *Y-zeolite* show S_{BET} of 872 and 677 m²/g, respectively, in good agreement with available data
 400 [11,68]. *LapRD* has a S_{BET} of 347 m²/g, which is consistent with the previous value from Edge
 401 [17] of 399 m²/g calculated from DFT calculations on the same laponite (Table 1).
 402 Slight bulk material density differences in-between these different studies may lead to minor
 403 changes of the microporous networks. By way of consequence, S_{BET} and H₂ uptake may slightly
 404 vary from one preparation to other, as illustrated by the mechanically-densified *MOF-177*
 405 from Zacharia et al. [46]. In addition, as outgassing conditions are not always identical from
 406 one study to the other, direct comparison with data from literature may not be
 407 straightforward. Whatever it is, the present benchmark exercise indicates a satisfactory
 408 agreement between our data and those available in state-of-the-art studies under similar
 409 operating conditions, thus validating the procedures used in the present work.

Figure 6

410 **Fig. 6.** H₂ isotherms of standards *MOF-177*, *LapRD*, *Y-zeolite* and *Activated carbon* from this study and
 411 from the literature [17,31,44–46] carried out at : (a) 77 K and 1 bar ; and (b) at 298 K and 120 bar.
 412 *LapRD* from Edge [17] is a Na-LaponiteRD similar to *LapRD* from this study.

413 3.5.2 H₂ isotherms of saponite and gel samples at 77 K - 1 bar

414 H₂ isotherms of saponites at 77 K – 1 bar show H₂ uptakes ranging from 0.01 to 0.03 wt% H₂
 415 for *Sap1.2_Ni-pillars* and for *Sap1.2_Ni-edges1*, respectively. These slight uptake differences
 416 being within the uncertainty (around ± 0.01 wt% H₂ at 1 bar, calculated from *LapRD*
 417 reproducibility measurements), no significant increase of H₂ uptake capacity could be
 418 identified for Ni-saponites compared to *Sap1.2* whose H₂ uptake stands at 0.02 wt% (Figs. 7a-
 419 c).
 420 The precursor gel *Gel_Sap1.2* is a significant exception with a maximum uptake of 0.19 wt%
 421 H₂ at 1 bar H₂ pressure, which is by one order of magnitude higher than the capacity of *Sap1.2*
 422 under the same conditions (Fig. 7d).

Figure 7

423
 424 **Fig. 7.** H₂ isotherms carried out at 1 bar and 77 K of *Sap1.2* compared to : (a) *Sap1.2_Ni-interl.* and
 425 *Sap1.2_Ni-pillars* ; (b) *Sap1.2_Ni-edges1,2,3* ; (c) *Sap1.2_Ni_surface* ; and (d) *Gel_Sap1.2*.

3.5.3 H₂ isotherms of saponite and gel samples at 298 K – 120 bar

427 H₂ isotherms acquisition at high pressure on these materials can be very challenging as the
 428 following pitfalls must be overcome: (1) gas leakage due to the high diffusivity of H₂, (2) a low
 429 signal to noise ratio due to the low H₂ uptake capacity combined with low S_{BET} of most saponite
 430 samples, and (3) poorly-resolved volumetric due to the small mass of saponite (~ 250 mg) that
 431 can be loaded in the ~ 200 mm³ sample holder. Having in mind all these limitations, one can
 432 conclude from Fig. 8a that H₂ uptake on saponites, with and without Ni²⁺ in the structure, is
 433 very low, remaining < 0.05 wt% for all saponite samples investigated.
 434 Contrastingly, the precursor gel *Gel_Sap1.2* shows a maximum H₂ uptake of 0.12 wt% H₂ at
 435 120 bar and 298 K, and a very good reproducibility between the two replicate measurements
 436 performed of the same sample (Fig. 8b).

437 **Fig 8.** H₂ isotherms carried out at 120 bar and 298 K on: (a) *Sap1.2*, *Sap1.2_Ni-pillars*, *Sap1.2_Ni-*
 438 *edges1,3*; and (d) *Gel_Sap1.2* and *Gel_Sap1.2** (replicate), whose isotherm was measured on the same
 439 apparatus.
 440

4. Discussion

4.1 Effect of porosity and Ni²⁺ intercalation on H₂ adsorption on saponite and nano-crystallized precursor at 1 bar – 77 K

445 At 1 bar and 77 K, all saponites show H₂ uptakes from 0.01 to 0.03 wt% H₂ and no clear
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3 446 tendency is highlighted in between Ni-saponites that could be assigned to a specific Ni
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5 447 configuration in the structure. The *Gel_sap1.2* shows a higher H₂ sorption capacity with a H₂
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7 448 uptake of 0.19 wt% H₂ at 1 bar - 77 K. Only few data from literature are available on smectite
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10 449 H₂ sorption capacities [25,69,70]. Gil et al. [25] recorded ~ 0.2 wt% H₂ at 1 bar and 77 K on an
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13 450 Al-pillared montmorillonite. These high uptakes are correlated with the presence of
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15 451 microporosity whose volume (as determined by N₂ adsorption) reaches up to 0.080 cm³/g,
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18 452 which is well above values ~ 0.001 - 0.003 cm³/g determined for Ni-saponites in the present
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21 453 study (Table 1). The apparent hysteresis on saponite N₂ isotherms (Fig. 5) is likely produced by
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23 454 inter-particles pore space, corresponding to a more complex porous network in comparison
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26 455 to conventional mesoporosity [71,72]. This is confirmed by the absence of a sorption plateau
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29 456 at P/P₀ = 1. Here, the desorption curves of *Sap1.2_Ni-pillars* and *Sap1.2_Ni-edges1,2,3* display
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31 457 hysteresis loops larger than for *Sap1.2* and *Sap1.2_Ni-interl.*, while having similar adsorption
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34 458 branches (Fig. 5). As these samples cannot be considered as microporous, it is difficult to
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36 459 interpret these differences in term of pore geometries as classically commonly assumed [73].
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39 460 However it is likely that Ni²⁺ and Ni(OH)₂ clusters/pillars affect *Sap1.2* structure in a sufficient
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41 461 manner to impact capillary condensation during desorption by two main aspects: (1) the
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44 462 variation of hydration energy of smectite interlayer cation (*Sap1.2_Ni-interl.*); and (2) the
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47 463 creation of “holes” in between pillars that may remain hydrated even at very low RH
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49 464 conditions (*Sap1.2_Ni-pillars*) as attested by the weight loss attributed to interlayer water
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52 465 removal above 150 °C (Fig. 4). In fact, intercalation of Ni²⁺ in the saponite structure mainly
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54 466 influences water retention as revealed by XRD and TGA data. Such effect is particularly visible
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57 467 for both the *Sap1.2_Ni-interl.* and *Sap1.2_Ni-pillars* (Figs. 2 and 4). However, there is no
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3 468 increase of H₂ adsorption through the creation of Ni²⁺-bearing crystallographic sites compared
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6 469 to the Na-saturated *Sap1.2*.

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11 470 Concerning the *Sap1.2_Ni-surface* sample, the lower SSA may be explained according to Sarac
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14 471 Oztuna et al. [74]. The SSAs of functionalized porous subtract are slightly lower than that of
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16 472 bare subtract because of pore clogging by nanoparticles. However, these authors have
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18 473 observed that the SSA gradually increased when Ni nanoparticles loading increases from 1.5
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20 474 wt% to 20 wt%. Therefore, Ni amount may be optimized in order to minimize the SSA
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22 475 reduction while providing the catalytic performances of metal loading.

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24 476 The *Gel_sap1.2* is an exception as its micropores volume (0.029 cm³/g, as determined by N₂
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26 477 adsorption) is much higher than the one of the well-crystallized saponites, but remains
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28 478 relatively small for such a high H₂ uptake. This observation questions either the importance of
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30 479 the textural control on H₂ adsorption or the relevance of N₂ adsorption results to characterize
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32 480 the micropore volume available for H₂, as discussed below.

33 34 35 481 **4.2 Effect of outgassing condition**

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39 482 Outgassing conditions, i.e. temperature and duration of the outgas prior to volumetric
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41 483 measurements, have a strong impact on H₂ adsorption, as highlighted by Edge [17] study on
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43 484 laponite who tested different degassing temperatures (from ambient temperature, and up to
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45 485 160 °C under secondary vacuum condition) and observed very different H₂ uptakes (from 0.08
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47 486 to 0.24 wt% H₂). Ziemiański & Derkowski [29] also reveal that H₂ uptake on montmorillonite
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49 487 significantly decreases with increasing outgassing temperature from 40 to 210 °C. Here,
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51 488 sample outgassing at 70 °C, 150 °C, and 300 °C were carried out on *Sap1.2_Ni-pillars* in order
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53 489 to evaluate the effect of outgassing temperature on H₂ adsorption (Fig. 9). In particular, the
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55 490 thermal treatment during outgassing impacts the hydration state inside the interlayer space.
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491 Here, a temperature outgas of 70 °C, instead of a routine 150 °C treatment, results in a
492 significant sorption capacity increase from 0.05 wt% to 0.12 wt% H₂ at 77 K and 1 bar.
493 Adsorption isotherms recorded after outgassing the sample at 150 °C or 300 °C are nearly
494 identical. As previously observed from TGA results on this sample, dehydration is initiated at
495 low RH and nearly fully completed at ~ 150 °C, and dehydroxylation of Ni(OH)₂ pillars occurs
496 at ~ 400 °C. Then it is likely than sample outgassing at 150 °C or 300 °C lead to a partial or
497 complete dehydration of *Sap1.2_Ni-pillars* interlayer space, leading to its collapse despite the
498 presence of pillars in between. Then such a collapse may prevent H₂ and N₂ to access these
499 sorption sites. On the contrary, outgassing at 70 °C may allow the preservation of the pillars
500 structure. In this case, the *d*₀₀₁-spacing remains at about 14 Å. This value compares with 9.35
501 Å in the uncharged anhydrous analogue, talc. Because of the Ni(OH)₂ pillars, the interlayer
502 height of *Sap1.2_Ni-pillars* is therefore $d = (14 - 9.35) \text{ \AA} = 4.65 \text{ \AA}$. This value is slightly higher
503 than the kinetic diameter of H₂ (2.89 Å) and may be close to the optimum for H₂ to access the
504 interlayer sorption sites [75]. These measurements nicely demonstrate the importance of the
505 interlayer height for H₂ adsorption and the benefit of Ni(OH)₂ pillaring. We note that water
506 hydration also allows to tune the interlayer height and may thus promote H₂ adsorption
507 [23,29]. However, the outgassing step (heat and vacuum), that is a prerequisite before
508 carrying out adsorption isotherms, may compromise a proper control of the hydration state
509 of the samples as demonstrated by all our measurements performed after outgassing at 150
510 °C (Fig. 7).

Figure 9 (Discussion)

511
512 **Fig. 9.** H₂ isotherms at 1 bar and 77K of *Sap1.2_Ni-pillars* at various outgassing and analysis conditions.
513 Outgas temperatures of 70 °C, 150 °C, and 300 °C were tested, and equilibration time was increased
514 to 300 s instead of 60 s.

515 In addition, a higher equilibration time (i.e. t = 300 s at each pressure increment instead of
516 routine analysis t = 60 s, resulting in > 30 h of acquisition time for a complete isotherm) was
517 also tested to evaluate H₂ adsorption kinetic. Indeed, H₂ diffusion to the adsorption site may
518 also have to be accounted for the adsorption properties of the material. However, no positive
519 effect related to the equilibration time was clearly recorded here on H₂ uptake.

520 **4.3 Effect of SSA influence on hydrogen adsorption capacity in porous** 521 **materials**

522 Several studies have already revealed the linear relationship between H₂ adsorption and the
523 specific surface area at 1 bar and 77 K on different types of porous materials [30,76,77]. Such

1 524 a trend is also observed here (Fig. 10, colourful symbols), up to almost 500 m²/g for the upper
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3 525 SSA range corresponding to laponite.

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5 526 It is quite clear that samples having a high SSA, also display a high microporosity. In the case
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8 527 of both *LapRD* or *Gel_Sap1.2* the $S_{\mu\text{pore}}$ (340 m²/g and 77 m²/g) stand for ~ 98% and ~ 50% of
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11 528 S_{BET} (347 m²/g and 145 m²/g), respectively (Table 1). Such a conclusion has also been reached
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13 529 previously [31] for MOFs and activated carbons. Therefore, it is likely that micropores are
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16 530 responsible for much of the H₂ adsorption capacity. This observation makes sense when
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18 531 considering that a good match in-between micropores and H₂ kinetic diameter (2.89 Å) is a
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21 532 prerequisite for enhanced H₂ adsorption.

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24 533 We also point out that N₂ BET measurements do not allow probing the interlayer space. Thus,
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27 534 it is coherent that clay samples whose interlayer space has collapsed because of outgassing at
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30 535 150 °C are all plotted along this linear correlation in between H₂ adsorption and the specific
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32 536 surface. It also explains why *Sap1.2_Ni-pillars* outgassed at 70 °C, whose interlayer is still
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35 537 accessible to H₂, plots well above this line.

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Figure 10

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539 **Fig. 10.** H₂ uptakes of clay minerals from this study and the literature at 1 bar - 77 K and 120 bar – 298
540 K. The linear trend correlating SSA and H₂ uptake was calculated at 1 bar - 77 K for saponite and
541 laponite. *: *Sap1.2_Ni-pillars* with temperature outgas of 70 °C.

542 **4.4 Performance of saponite and related gel at 120 bar – 298 K**

543 All saponites show H₂ uptakes < 0.05 wt% at 120 bar and 298 K, and the *Gel_sap1.2* shows a
544 higher H₂ sorption capacity of 0.12 wt% H₂. At ambient temperature and above, Mondelli et
545 al. [69] and Bardelli et al. [70] recorded H₂ sorption capacities of ~ 0.20 and 0.25 wt% H₂ at 90
546 °C and 80 bar H₂ pressure on Na-montmorillonite and purified clay fraction (mainly illite-
547 smectite) of a Callovo-Oxfordian claystone, respectively. However, these values are intriguing
548 for two reasons. First, they are very high regarding both the elevated temperature condition
549 and the low specific surface area of these materials (< 40 m²/g). Second, they slightly increase
550 with temperature from 28 to 90 °C [70], which is not thermodynamically consistent. Recently,

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3 552 130 m²/g does not exceed 0.02 wt% at 298 K and 145 bar. They also confirmed that this H₂
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5 553 uptake logically decreases significantly with temperature increase.
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8 554 The linear relationship in between S_{BET} (as measured by N₂ adsorption) and H₂ uptake does
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11 555 not seem to be valid at high pressure and ambient temperature (Fig. 10, grey symbols). H₂
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13 556 sorption capacities drastically decrease as temperature increases, and that pressure increase
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16 557 does not compensate for this decrease. In the case of saponite, H₂ uptake is below 0.05 wt%
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18 558 H₂ at 298 K and 100 bar. Clay-related materials with higher S_{BET}, like *Gel_Sap1.2* and laponites
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21 559 (*LapRD*; [17]), do adsorb modest amount of H₂ under such conditions (> 0.2 wt%), but SSA in
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24 560 itself is not sufficient to predict their H₂ adsorption capacity. For example, the *Gel_Sap1.2*
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26 561 shows similar H₂ uptake at 120 bar and 298 K than laponites despite contrasting SSA values
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28 562 (SSA = 145 and 392 - 475 m²/g, respectively). Thus, the SSA and micropore volume determined
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31 563 by N₂ adsorption does not seem to be relevant to characterize the properties of the materials
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34 564 with respect to H₂ adsorption, at least at high pressure and ambient temperature. Ziemiański
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36 565 & Derkowski [29] clearly reveal that micropore volume determined by CO₂, a molecule that
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39 566 display a kinetic diameter closer to H₂ (2.89 and 3.3 Å for H₂ and CO₂ respectively), is much
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42 567 more appropriate.
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45 568 **4.5 Gels of clays: new perspectives for H₂ sorption ?**

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49 569 The emphasis for much research on H₂ storage has been placed in the limiting requirements
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51 570 for mobile applications, hitherto excluding clays because of their intrinsic weight. But large-
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54 571 scale storages do not bear the same constraints. In this context, clay minerals have several
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56 572 very attractive properties such as large surface area, low cost, and environmental safety.
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59 573 Representing volumetric density (i.e. kgH₂/m³) instead of gravimetric density (i.e. wt% H₂) is
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574 particularly relevant when comparing different materials, as their mass densities may be very
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3 575 different. Fig. 11 compares H₂ storage capacities at 298 K, a temperature of interest for large
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5 576 scale storage, for both *Gel_Sap1.2* and the well-studied *MOF-177*, at two different pressure:
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8 577 30 and 120 bar. First, by strictly comparing their volumetric density, i.e. their mass capacity
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10 578 for storing H₂ in a given volume (here 1 m³), *Gel_Sap1.2* shows a comparable performance
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13 579 with *MOF-177*. In particular, at 30 bar and 298 K both materials have nearly identical H₂
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15 580 volumetric densities of 0.5 kgH₂/m³. Ambient temperature associated with a few tens of bars
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18 581 being ideal conditions for an industrial application, like a stationary underground H₂ storage,
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21 582 it is thus interesting to notice the high potential of *Gel_Sap1.2*.
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24 583 Even if MOFs, as well as *Gel_Sap1.2*, do not display sufficient H₂ uptake to make them useful
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27 584 for H₂ storage at ambient temperature, one may notice that a low cost and easy-to-produce
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29 585 material like gel performs as well as very expensive MOFs. Thus, this gel of clay material is a
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32 586 new and promising porous material. Its sorption capacities may be enhanced by compaction
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34 587 (increase the volumetric density) and by acid treatment, as classically used for enhancing
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37 588 specific surface area [27].
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40 589 Up to now, all the research effort on H₂ physisorption has focused on crystallized nano-
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43 590 materials (e.g. MOFs, zeolites, carbon nano-fibers) whose pore size is dimensioned to
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45 591 approach the kinetic diameter of the H₂ molecule. The alumino-silicate gel displays sorption
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48 592 capacities that are 2 to 5 times higher than their crystalline equivalent, even at ambient
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51 593 temperature. By definition, the so call *Gel_Sap1.2* is supposed to be amorphous, but XRD
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53 594 patterns (Fig. 2c) attest for the presence of small or poorly crystalline phases. In addition, it
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56 595 displays high specific surface area (~ 150 m²/g) and high micropore volumes ($V_{\mu\text{pores}} = 0.029$
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58 596 cm³/g). This “gel” is therefore the antithesis of all crystallized substrates studied so far. A
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597 specific point to further investigate to better understand the global structure of this material
598 and more specifically the localization of micropores. Its ambient sorption properties are still
599 too low to justify a stationary storage application, but an improvement in its capacity by a
600 factor of 2 would already allow a significant gain compared to classical pressurized storage.

Figure 11

601
602 **Fig. 11.** Hydrogen volumetric densities of *Gel_Sap1.2* at 30 bar and 120 bar compared to *MOF-177* at
603 ambient temperature. The black arrow indicates the density objective to reach to have an economic
604 interest in storing H₂ physisorbed inside clays instead of gaseous storing in pressurized tank.

606 5. Conclusion

607 N₂ and H₂ isotherms measurements performed at 77 K – 1 bar and 298 K – 120 bar on *Sap1.2*
608 and Ni-saponites record low SSAs ranging from 9 to 40 m²/g and modest H₂ uptakes of ~ 0.03

609 wt% H₂ at 77 K – 1 bar, and < 0.05 wt% H₂ at 298 K – 120 bar. These low values indicate that
610 Ni functionalization do not create specific crystallographic sites for H₂ adsorption. However, it
611 is observed that H₂ uptake is strongly controlled by external conditions, in particular
612 outgassing temperature that influences the interlayer space opening through its hydration
613 state. Measurements on Ni-pillared saponite highlight that an outgas of 70 °C preserves the
614 interlayer space porosity for H₂ adsorption, in comparison to other saponites routinely
615 outgassed at 150 °C. It is likely that H₂ can only access the inter particles pore space and the
616 basal and lateral adsorption sites in these latter samples outgassed at 150 °C. This is supported
617 by the linear correlation in between SSA and H₂ uptake at 1 bar and 77 K, illustrating that
618 neither N₂ nor H₂ enter porosity inside the structure.

619 The precursor gel (*Gel_Sap1.2*) used for saponite synthesis, is an exception as it displays an
620 SSA of 145 m²/g together with a high microporosity and an H₂ uptake of 0.19 wt% at 77 K and
621 1 bar, and up to 0.12 wt% at 298 K and 120 bar. This latter uptake is equivalent to what can
622 achieve the *MOF-177* under identical conditions. Further investigations on precursor gel
623 materials are needed for their microporous features and good potential for high H₂ uptakes.

624

625 **Acknowledgements**

626 This work was financially supported by ORANO industry and the ANR OCCAMH2. The
627 geochemistry-mineralogy platform of ISTERre (Grenoble, France) used for most measurements
628 is partially funded by a grant from Labex OSUG@2020 (investissements d'avenir, ANR10-
629 LABX56").

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